

LOCALIZED HYBRIDIZATION USING BORON FIBERS: A ROUTE TO IMPROVE OPEN HOLE COMPRESSIVE PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

In this study we propose a novel localized hybridization concept to enhance longitudinal compressive performance of composites containing open holes. The concept involves hybridization in the form of selective placement of individual boron fibres locally near the vicinity of a hole within 0° plies of a quasi-isotropic laminate made from a carbon-epoxy prepreg. The manufacturing of these novel hybrid laminates is realized using an in-house developed fibre placement fixture to precisely place the boron fibres at the required locations. The mechanical performance of the manufactured concept is benchmarked against a non-hybrid baseline laminate under quasi-static compressive loading following the ASTM D6484 standard. The proposed hybridisation strategy results in a significant ($\approx 35\%$) increase in compressive strength over the corresponding baseline laminate. The improvement in compressive performance can be attributed to changes in failure mechanisms due to the presence of the boron fibres within the hybrid laminates, as revealed by post-test failure analysis (using X-ray scans and scanning electron microscopy) and finite element simulations. Our research demonstrates the success of this first of its kind locally hybrid design aimed at improving open hole compressive performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite structures often include features like holes to serve various operational purposes, including cable or pipeline routing, fastener installations, and other functional requirements. However, these holes typically lead to localized stress concentrations [1]. Under compressive loading, these stress concentrations may result in microbuckling and unstable kink band growth near the hole edge, leading to catastrophic failure [2,3]. Hence, to improve the overall load-bearing capacity of such structures, it becomes crucial to devise a strategy to delay or suppress the progression of damage arising in the form of kink band growth from the hole.

In a previous study, by using commercial boron-carbon hybrid prepregs, Garulli et al. [4] observed that, for an edge-notched laminate under compression, both in-plane and out-of-plane kinking in carbon fibres can be arrested by the presence of boron fibres [4]. When the propagating kink band reaches a boron fibre, damage is interrupted and deflected by formation of a longitudinal split at the boron-epoxy interface. This work aims to utilize this deflection mechanism by developing an open hole-focused design wherein a patch of boron fibres is placed in accordance with the localized stress distribution around the hole.

The process involves hybridization of 0° plies of a quasi-isotropic carbon epoxy laminate by placing individual boron fibres aligned at 0° direction selectively at regular intervals in the transverse direction from the hole edge as shown in Fig. 1. To realize this, an in-house manufacturing procedure has been developed. The performance of hybrid laminates is benchmarked against a non-hybrid baseline laminate configuration under open hole compression as per ASTM D6484 test standard [5]. This study provides a practical localized approach for designers to enhance compressive strength near structural features like open holes, without affecting the overall global structural performance.

2 CONCEPT DESIGN, MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURING

2.1 Concept Design

In this work, we aim at improving the open hole compressive performance of a quasi-isotropic laminate ($[45_{10}/-45_{10}/0_{10}/90_{10}]_{3S}$) by embedding boron fibres within the block of 0_{10} plies resulting in a hybrid laminate ($[45_{10}/-45_{10}/0_{\text{Hybrid}}/90_{10}]_{3S}$). Each 0_{Hybrid} ply-block comprises of boron fibres embedded in the centre of 10 ultrathin carbon epoxy plies. However, the length of the boron fibres is relatively short compared to the overall length of the carbon fibres in 0° plies. Fig. 1 presents a schematic representation of 0° plies of a baseline and hybrid laminate samples tested in this work. The presence of the boron fibres is restricted to a local region in the vicinity of the hole resulting in a localized hybrid ply configuration. Fig. 1(c) presents a close-up view of the region near the hole for a hybrid sample showing distribution of the boron fibres. The variation in length of boron fibres follows the profile of variation of longitudinal stress with respect to the transverse distance from the edge of the hole.

Figure 1: Schematic representation a 0° ply in the open hole specimens used in this study (a) baseline (non-hybrid) specimen (b) hybrid specimen (c) X-ray scan obtained during manufacturing stage, showing distribution of boron fibres within one hybrid 0° ply (note-figure (a) and (b) not to scale, all dimensions are in mm).

2.2 Materials

The required laminates were manufactured using a 15 gsm MR70/TP402 prepreg. The properties of this material have been reported by Garulli et al. [6]. For hybridization, 4-mil boron fibres supplied by Speciality Materials have been used. Boron fibres exhibit a unique combination of high compressive strength, high modulus and a large diameter [7]. The key material properties of boron fibres are presented in Table 1.

Property	Units	4-mil boron fibre
Diameter	μm	102
Density	g/cc	2.61
Thermal Expansion	$\text{PPM}/^\circ\text{C}$	4.5
Tensile Strength	MPa	4000
Tensile Modulus	GPa	428
Compression Strength	MPa	>6000
Hardness	Knoop	3200

Table 1: Properties of the boron fibre used in this work [7].

2.3 Manufacturing

The manufacturing of the hybrid laminates was performed by a procedure developed in-house specifically for this study. As can be seen in Fig.1 (c), the hybrid plies contain individual boron fibres of different lengths placed at specific locations in the vicinity of the hole. This requirement led to the development of an in-house fibre placement fixture as shown in Fig. 2 (a). The overview of the whole process is presented in the form of a schematic diagram in Fig. 2 (b). The first step involves placing one ply of MR70/TP402 prepreg over the bottom plate of the fixture. The next step (Step-2 in schematic) involves placing the boron fibres one by one at required locations on the bottom prepreg. The guide plate provides a straight edge to align boron fibres parallel to the 0° direction (y-direction in Fig. 2(a)). The pitch between the boron fibres is controlled by moving the bottom plate with respect to the guide plate in x-direction. The bottom plate of the fixture is mounted over a linear x-stage which allows relative motion between the guide plate and the bottom plate in the x-direction as shown in Fig. 2(a). Once all

the required fibres are placed on the bottom prepreg, the guide plate along with the z-stage is removed from the fixture and another prepreg ply laid up on top of the previously arranged boron fibres and bottom prepreg, as shown in Step-3 in the schematic. Thereafter, the stack containing the two prepreg layers sandwiching the array of boron fibres between them, is brought onto a vacuum table and is subjected to vacuum for 30 minutes (Step-4). A caul plate is used during this step as shown in Step-4. Thereafter, the whole process (except Step-2) is repeated until four more top and bottom prepreg plies are added to the hybrid ply block.

In the end, one hybrid ply block comprises of a total of ten MR70/TP402 plies containing one array of boron fibres embedded in the middle. This one hybrid ply-block is represented as 0_{Hybrid} in the overall stacking sequence of $[45_{10}/-45_{10}/0_{Hybrid}/90_{10}]_{3S}$. In a similar way a total of six such hybrid 0° ply blocks are prepared and a final layup of $[45_{10}/-45_{10}/0_{Hybrid}/90_{10}]_{3S}$ is stacked. The curing of the layups is performed as per the curing parameters specified by manufacturer's datasheet [8]. The baseline laminates with stacking sequence $[45_{10}/-45_{10}/0_{10}/90_{10}]_{3S}$ were manufactured using similar manufacturing conditions except the process for the baseline laminates does not require the steps mentioned in Fig. 2 (b) due to the absence of boron fibres. The test specimens were machined out of the cured panels and the holes were drilled and reamed carefully to final dimensions as per ASTM D6484 [5]. The nominal dimensions of the specimens are shown in the schematic in Fig. 1 (a).

Figure 2: (a) Image of the fibre placement fixture used
(b) Schematic representation of the steps involved in preparing a hybrid ply;

3 TESTING AND MODELLING

3.1 Testing Methodology

The proposed hybrid concept was assessed against the baseline configuration by testing samples containing open holes subjected to compressive loading following the procedure described in ASTM D6484 [5]. A total of five samples for each configuration were tested. The load was introduced at a constant crosshead displacement rate of 1 mm/min. The test was stopped once a significant drop in load was observed. During the test, digital image correlation was employed to study development of strains in the vicinity of the hole. Fig. 3 shows an image of the test setup showing the main components. After the test, the samples were carefully removed from the test fixture. For the purpose of visual examination, digital photographs of tested specimens were obtained using a flatbed scanner. Thereafter, representative samples from both the baseline and hybrid configuration were further examined using two-dimensional X-ray scans. The specimens were then carefully dissected along the fracture path to examine the fracture surface using a scanning electron microscope (SEM).

Figure 3: Experimental setup used for open hole compression testing using ASTM D6484.

3.2 Finite Element (FE) Modelling

A mesoscale modelling approach was used to understand the local stiffening effects due to the presence of additional reinforcement in the form of boron fibres around the hole. Two specimen models were generated: baseline and hybridised. Both specimen models follow the experimental specimen's dimensions as shown in Figs. 1 (a) and 4. The baseline specimen model consisted entirely of a carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) with uniform material properties. In the hybridised specimen model, the position, size, and shape of the hybrid regions (CFRP_H) were defined according to the boron fibre placement used in the experiments (Section 2.1). Both CFRP and CFRP_H regions were modelled as homogeneous and linear-elastic within the specimen models for computational efficiency. The numerical simulation was conducted using Abaqus 2024 [9]; a uniform compression displacement (maximum displacement = 3 mm) was applied at the transverse edge of the specimen models. Implicit static analysis was used. Throughout the numerical simulation of each specimen model, the local strain $\epsilon_y^{\text{local}}$ was measured by a 7 mm virtual extensometer at the edge of the hole as shown in Fig. 4. The data obtained from this virtual extensometer was compared with the data obtained from a comparable 7 mm virtual extensometer used in processing DIC data, to obtain experimental strain data.

Figure 4: FE model geometry (0° ply) for the hybridised specimen]

4 RESULTS

The experimental gross compressive stress-crosshead displacement plots for a representative hybrid and a baseline sample are shown in Fig. 5 (a). It can be observed that both laminate configurations follow a similar loading trace with a catastrophic drop in load towards the end of the test. However, the stress and displacement at which this drop occurs is significantly different. Fig. 5 (b) shows a bar graph of average gross compressive strength of five samples under each configuration (Baseline and Hybrid). It is observed that the hybrid samples exhibit close to 35% higher compressive strength compared to the baseline samples. To understand the influence on localized stiffness around hole due to presence of boron fibres, the local strain from DIC and the FE model are plotted against the gross compressive stress for the same representative baseline and hybrid samples in Fig. 6 (a). These results from both the model and experiments indicate an increase in local stiffness in the vicinity of the hole. Fig 6 (b) shows a corresponding change in local compressive modulus for both laminates. Further, a bar graph showing difference in stress concentration at the edge of the hole within 0° plies of both baseline and hybrid configurations is shown in Fig. 6(c).

Figure 5: (a) Trace of experimental compressive stress with respect to crosshead displacement for a representative hybrid and baseline sample (b) Bar graph showing the average gross strength observed experimentally in each laminate configuration. Note- The error bars in Fig. (b) indicate a ± 1 standard deviation interval.

Figure 6: (a) Trace of gross compressive stress with respect to local strain for baseline and hybrid configurations using a virtual extensometer near the edge of the hole obtained from the mesoscale FE model and experiments (b) Bar graph showing the localized compressive modulus observed both experimentally and with the mesoscale FE model in each laminate (c) Bar graph showing the stress concentration factor at the edge of the hole observed with the mesoscale FE model in each laminate

The post-test X-ray scans are shown in Fig.7. These scans reveal a difference in the extent of the spread of damage between baseline and hybrid configurations. It can be noted that the damage in the longitudinal direction is more widespread in case of hybrid samples, suggesting a difference in the internal failure mechanisms. Fig. 8 shows the SEM micrographs obtained after dissecting the samples along the fracture path growing transverse to the loading.

Fig. 7. Post OHC X-ray scan of (a) Baseline (b) Hybrid samples

Figure 8: Post OHC SEM micrograph of (a) Baseline (b) Hybrid samples

5 DISCUSSIONS

The results presented in Section 4 show that the proposed local hybridization design about an open hole in quasi-isotropic CFRP laminates was successful in significantly improving the compressive performance. The increase in compressive strength of the hybrid laminate when compared to the baseline one was close to 35%. This improvement can be attributed partially to the reduction in the stress concentration at the hole edge (Fig. 6(c)) and partly to the formation of longitudinal splits within the 0° ply in the case of the hybrid laminates (Fig. 8 (b)). These longitudinal splits interrupt the unstable progression of kink bands in the transverse direction. This phenomenon is similar to the one reported by Garulli et al. [4] where they studied the damage mechanisms in boron-carbon hybrid laminates under compressive loading for edge-notched specimens. In fact, the presence of the longitudinal splits in the hybrid laminates leads to the formation of isolated strips of carbon fibres. This isolation of strips of carbon fibres results in a delay of the unstable kink band growth in a 0° ply, thus increasing the overall load and displacement (Fig. 5 (a)) at which catastrophic failure occurs. The presence of boron fibres (Fig. 6(b)) influences the local stiffness as observed by stress-local strain plots obtain from DIC and the FE model. On the other hand, the baseline samples exhibited evidence of continuous kink band growth (Fig. 8(a)), resulting in catastrophic failure at a lower load.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This research demonstrates the potential to increase the compressive strength of CFRP laminates structural features using a first-of-its-kind tailored strategy exploiting boron fibres to stop kink band propagation. Ultra-thin CFRP prepreg plies were reinforced locally using boron fibres. This has been achieved developing an in-situ manufacturing process for individual boron-fibre placement locally within the plies. The performance of hybrid boron-carbon laminates was assessed against baseline laminates under open-hole compression. The hybrid laminates exhibited an improvement of by 35% open hole compressive strength compared to baseline non-hybrid quasi-isotropic laminates.

In conclusion, this study underscores the efficacy of a localized hybridization approach in improving the compressive performance with insignificant influence on stiffness and weight of the laminates, thus offering a practical localized solution for designers to improve compressive strength near structural details such as open hole features without affecting the overall structure at a global level.

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REFERENCES

- [1] C. Soutis, N.A. Fleck, Static Compression Failure of Carbon Fibre T800/924C Composite Plate with a Single Hole, *J Compos Mater* 24 (1990) 536–558. <https://doi.org/10.1177/002199839002400505>.
- [2] H. Suemasu, H. Takahashi, T. Ishikawa, On failure mechanisms of composite laminates with an open hole subjected to compressive load, *Compos Sci Technol* 66 (2006) 634–641. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compscitech.2005.07.042>.

- [3] H. Suemasu, Y. Naito, K. Gozu, Y. Aoki, Damage initiation and growth in composite laminates during open hole compression tests, *Advanced Composite Materials* 21 (2012) 209–220. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09243046.2012.723330>.
- [4] T. Garulli, T.J. Katafiasz, E.S. Greenhalgh, S.T. Pinho, Damage deflection and subsequent damage diffusion in carbon–boron fibre hybrid composites under longitudinal compression, *Compos B Eng* 291 (2025) 112025. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2024.112025>.
- [5] ASTM D6484/D6484M-23, Test Method for Open-Hole Compressive Strength of Polymer Matrix Composite Laminates, (2023). https://doi.org/10.1520/D6484_D6484M-23.
- [6] T. Garulli, T.J. Katafiasz, E.S. Greenhalgh, S.T. Pinho, A novel bio-inspired microstructure for improved compressive performance of multidirectional CFRP laminates, *Compos B Eng* 264 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesb.2023.110867>.
- [7] Boron Fiber Properties — Specialty Materials, (2025). <https://www.specmaterials.com/boron-fiber-test-page>.
- [8] NTPT ThinPreg™ 402 data sheet Version 1.6, (2017). <https://ntpt.tech/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/NTPT-DS-ThinPreg-402-May2017-v3.pdf>.
- [9] Abaqus/CAE | SIMULIA - Dassault Systèmes, (2024). <https://www.3ds.com/products/simulia/abaqus/cae>.